

Evaluation of wheat genotypes for drought tolerance according to physiological characteristics

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Wheat is an important cereal crop in human nutrition as well as a fodder plant for animals. Wheat grain yield decreases seriously due to water scarcity during growth and development. Physiological traits are important for screening different wheat genotypes against drought. We studied physiological traits (gas exchange parameters, photosynthesizing pigments content, relative water content, leaf area index) of durum and bread wheat genotypes under irrigated and drought conditions. Wheat genotypes with high indicators of studied traits are usually sensitive to drought stress. Wheat genotypes Sharg, Gyrmyzy bugda, Nurlu 99, 4thFEFWSN50, and Saratovskaya 29 were tolerant to drought stress.

Keywords: *Wheat, drought stress, photosynthesis, chlorophyll, relative water content, leaf area index, grain yield*

INTRODUCTION

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is ranked second among cereal crops in terms of total global production but ranked number one in terms of the total area under cultivation (FAO, 2018). The global wheat production in the 2022 year was 774 million metric tons. Globally wheat is responsible for 41% of cereal calorie intake, broken down as 35% and 74% in developing and developed countries, respectively (Shiferaw et al., 2013). Losses in wheat production are mainly due to abiotic factors such as drought, heat, and salinity. Usually, in the field, drought is accompanied by high temperatures, which increases in the post-anthesis growth stage of wheat. Along with classical breeding, morphological, physiological, biochemical indicators, as well as molecular markers are widely used in the study of drought tolerance in wheat. Physiological approaches have already demonstrated significant genetic gains in Australia and several developing countries of the International Wheat Improvement Network (Reynolds and Langridge, 2016). In recent studies, physiological indicators (gas exchange parameters, stay green phenotype, canopy temperature, cell membrane stability, fluorescence) are widely used in wheat breeding under drought conditions (Jatoi et al., 2011; Nowsherwan et al., 2018; Khadka et al., 2020). Increasing the efficiency of breeding

drought-tolerant wheat varieties by targeting physio-morphological traits requires a thorough understanding of the impact of drought at different growth stages (Khadka et al., 2020). Drought significantly decreased net photosynthesis, stomatal conductance, relative water contents, 100-grain weight, and grain yield in bread wheat genotypes (Wasaya et al., 2021). Plants are able to avoid the effects of drought stress by lowering leaf water potential and reducing transpirational water loss by closing stomatal apertures (Farooq et al. 2009). The foliar photosynthetic rate of higher plants is known to decrease as the relative water content and leaf water potential decrease (Lawlor and Cornic, 2002). Breeding high-yielding wheat genotypes for dry environments requires the identification of drought-tolerant and water-use-efficient germplasm for use in improvement programs (Tshikunde et al., 2018). Plants have evolved acclimation and adaptation mechanisms to cope with water deficit, including avoidance, escape from stress, and dehydration tolerance of the protoplast.

We aimed to study the effect of drought stress on some physiological traits of durum and bread wheat genotypes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Field experiments were conducted during the 2013-2014 growing season at the Plant Physiology

department of the Research Institute of Crop Husbandry, located in Apsheron peninsula (40°26' N, 49°52' E, 27 m low from sea level), Baku. Plant materials consisted of 8 durum wheat and 14 bread wheat genotypes. Sowing was performed in the third decade of October, at an average density of 400 seeds/m² with a mechanical planter in 1m x 10m plots, consisting of 7 rows placed 15 cm apart. Genotypes were grown in irrigated and rainfed plots with two replications. Irrigated plots were watered after the appearance of seedlings, at the stem elongation, anthesis, and grain-filling stages. Soil moisture content was determined at 0-20, 20-40, and 40-60 cm depths and was an average of 60% in irrigated and 30% in rainfed plots at the grain formation stage.

Measurements. Gas exchange parameters were measured by using Li-6400 XT Portable Photosynthesis System (Li-COR Biosciences, Lincoln, Nebraska, USA) at the booting growth stage of wheat (Feekes Stage 10). Chlorophyll a, b, and carotenoid contents were determined by the modified method of Lichtenthaler (1987). Relative water content (RWC) was determined by weighing the fresh mass, turgid mass, and dry mass of the flag leaf. The following formula was used for the calculation of RWC: $RWC, \% = (FM-DM)/(TM-DM) \times 100$. Leaf area was measured by using LI-

3100 Area Meter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Drought stress caused a reduction of gas exchange parameters (Table 1). Decreases of 19% for P_n, 23% for g_s, and 19% for E were observed under drought stress conditions. The most significant reduction of gas exchange parameters was observed in the genotypes Barakatli 95, Gyrgyzy bugda, Akinchi 84, and Azamatli 95. Non-significant reduction of gas exchange parameters was observed in genotypes Garagylchyg 2, Shiraslan 23, Nurlu 99, Tale 38, Pirshahin 1, 12ndFAWWON97, Saratovskaya 29 genotypes. The gas exchange parameters such as net photosynthesis (P_n), stomatal conductance (g_s), and transpiration rate (E) were reduced under both drought stress conditions compared with control (well-watered). Decreases of 30% and 70% for P_n, 45% and 81% for g_s, and 45% and 80% for E were observed under mild drought and severe drought conditions, respectively (Wasaya et al., 2021).

Water stress caused a reduction in the photosynthetic pigment content. The average reduction of Chl a, b, and Car (x+c) was 28%, 28.7%, and 26.2% respectively (Table 2).

Table 1. Effect of drought stress on gas exchange parameters of wheat genotypes

Genotypes	Photosynthesis rate, P _n		Stomatal conductance, g _s		Intercellular CO ₂ concentration, C _i		Transpiration rate, E	
	irrigated	drought	irrigated	drought	irrigated	drought	irrigated	drought
<i>Triticum durum</i> Desf								
Garagylchyg 2	11.01	10.65	0.149	0.132	246	226	2.32	2.23
Vugar	12.27	11.31	0.232	0.175	270	250	2.38	2.28
Shiraslan 23	11.91	10.57	0.191	0.182	267	264	2.17	1.95
Barakatli 95	14.6	9.99	0.277	0.150	265	254	2.97	1.74
Alinja 84	15.28	12.57	0.196	0.141	222	216	3.18	2.33
Tartar	13.46	10.21	0.199	0.116	244	217	3.10	2.21
Sharg	10.82	8.85	0.170	0.131	283	232	2.48	2.13
Gyrgyzy bugda	14.24	7.9	0.215	0.122	261	266	2.84	1.86
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.								
Nurlu 99	10.12	8.62	0.268	0.225	297	303	1.94	1.77
Gobustan	11.58	11.53	0.181	0.132	253	219	2.69	2.28
Akinchi 84	12.67	7.67	0.191	0.092	247	227	2.83	1.65
Giyamatli 2/17	10.82	6.86	0.158	0.123	246	273	2.39	1.93
Gyrgyzy gul 1	15.42	11.85	0.259	0.183	251	252	3.72	2.65
Azamatli 95	12.43	8.54	0.224	0.121	265	247	3.29	1.93
Tale 38	14.89	13.58	0.280	0.261	263	263	4.14	3.82
Ruzi 84	14.02	11.16	0.517	0.412	325	320	3.07	2.49
Pirshahin 1	15.92	14.57	0.467	0.454	297	305	3.59	3.34
12 nd FAWWON 97	11.52	10.68	0.217	0.194	274	270	3.60	2.96
Gunashli	13.71	12.64	0.336	0.248	288	269	3.64	3.41
4thFEFWSN50	8.18	6.53	0.306	0.285	322	339	2.29	2.18
Dagdash	10.23	7.04	0.119	0.114	227	283	2.17	1.55
Saratovskaya 29	11.6	9.44	0.137	0.132	237	262	2.71	2.33

Table 2. Photosynthetic pigment content under irrigated (I) and drought stress (D) conditions

Genotypes	Chl a, mg/g dry mass		Chl b, mg/g dry mass		Chl a+b, mg/g dry mass		Car (x+c), mg/g dry mass		Chl a/b		Chl (a+b)/car(x+c)	
	I	D	I	D	I	D	I	D			I	D
<i>Triticum durum</i> Desf												
Garagylchyg 2	6.34	3.08	2.56	1.75	8.90	4.83	1.48	0.63	2.47	1.77	6.01	7.66
Vugar	6.29	6.04	2.70	2.70	8.98	8.74	1.33	1.40	2.33	2.23	6.75	6.24
Shiraslan 23	5.54	4.16	2.82	2.15	8.36	6.31	1.02	1.01	1.96	1.93	8.23	6.27
Barakatli 95	6.85	5.36	2.91	2.40	9.75	7.76	1.53	1.15	2.36	2.23	6.37	6.75
Alinja 84	5.68	4.72	2.67	2.35	8.36	7.06	1.24	0.98	2.13	2.01	6.73	7.16
Tartar	10.0	4.57	3.99	1.83	14.0	6.40	2.08	1.09	2.52	2.50	6.74	5.87
Sharg	5.16	3.97	1.93	1.47	7.08	5.44	1.46	1.36	2.67	2.69	4.84	4.01
Gyrmyzy bugda	5.84	5.04	2.07	1.79	7.91	6.83	1.47	1.49	2.81	2.81	5.38	4.57
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.												
Nurlu 99	6.06	3.12	2.42	1.21	8.48	4.33	1.45	1.03	2.51	2.59	5.83	4.22
Gobustan	7.82	3.23	3.04	1.35	10.9	4.58	1.65	0.82	2.57	2.40	6.57	5.56
Akinchi 84	7.98	4.77	3.12	1.90	11.1	6.67	1.87	1.43	2.55	2.51	5.92	4.67
Giymatli 2/17	6.63	4.97	2.87	1.78	9.50	6.75	1.37	1.18	2.31	2.78	6.93	5.74
Gyrmyzy gul 1	8.02	5.99	3.10	2.32	11.1	8.31	1.70	1.33	2.59	2.59	6.54	6.24
Azamatli 95	5.88	5.17	2.37	2.17	8.25	7.34	1.29	1.34	2.48	2.39	6.39	5.48
Tale 38	7.52	5.86	3.01	2.26	10.5	8.12	1.58	1.44	2.50	2.59	6.65	5.62
Ruzi 84	5.92	4.23	2.23	1.72	8.15	5.95	1.60	1.25	2.66	2.47	5.09	4.75
Pirshahin 1	5.31	3.58	2.56	1.49	7.87	5.07	1.21	1.31	2.08	2.41	6.50	4.48
12 nd FAWWON 97	6.48	5.25	2.86	2.24	9.34	7.49	1.40	1.41	2.27	2.34	6.68	5.30
Gunashli	6.46	3.13	2.44	1.16	8.90	4.28	1.59	1.25	2.64	2.70	5.60	3.42
4 th FEFWSN50	6.97	5.42	2.94	2.18	9.90	7.60	1.61	1.41	2.37	2.48	6.16	5.40
Dagdash	7.34	6.35	2.77	2.38	10.1	8.73	1.73	1.87	2.65	2.66	5.83	4.66
Saratovskaya 29	7.20	6.79	2.73	2.59	9.93	9.38	1.71	1.65	2.64	2.62	5.82	5.67

An increase in Car(x+c) content was detected in some genotypes under drought stress. A strong reduction of the pigment content was revealed in the flag leaf of the wheat genotypes Garagylchyg 2, Tartar, Gobustan, and Akinchi 84 while less reduction was detected in the genotypes Vugar, Gyrmyzy bugda, Azamatli 95, Dagdash and Saratovskaya 29. The Chl a/b ratio decreased in half of the genotypes. It did not change in the genotypes Gyrmyzy bugda, Gyrmyzy gul 1, and increased in 9 genotypes. The Chl(a+b)/Car(x+c) ratio decreased in almost all genotypes, indicating more susceptibility of chlorophylls than carotenoids to water stress. Water stress had a significant impact on the concentration of some carotenoids (neoxantin, violaxantin), chlorophyll a and b in *Solanum aethiopicum* (Mibei et al., 2017).

Drought stress had a non-significant effect on relative water content (RWC) in flag leaves of wheat genotypes (Fig.1). The RWC in the flag leaf of wheat genotypes was an average of 84% under irrigation, and 79.9% under drought stress conditions. This parameter was relatively lower in genotype Nurlu 99 with the earliest heading time. The RWC of the flag leaf remains relatively high compared to the rate of photosynthesis and pigment content. The RWC was significantly decreased in leaves of all varieties, suggesting higher water loss under drought conditions (Duvnjak et al., 2023).

Drought stress affected water-related parameters (osmotic potential, leaf water potential, and relative water content) in wheat using nitrogen (Ullah et al., 2022).

The leaf area index (LAI) quantifies the amount of leaf area in an ecosystem and is a critical variable in processes such as photosynthesis, respiration, and precipitation interception (Alton, 2016). The leaf area index (LAI) is a critical vegetation structural variable and is essential in the feedback of vegetation to the climate system (Fang et al., 2019). Water stress caused a reduction in the leaf area index of wheat genotypes. The LAI is greater in wheat genotypes Garagylchyg 2, Vugar, Barakatli 95, Giymatly 2/17, Gyrmyzy gul 1, and Tale 38 under irrigated conditions. The mentioned genotypes, as well as wheat genotypes Akinchi 84, Ruzi 84, and Pirshahin 1 are characterized by strong reduction of leaf assimilation area (Fig.2).

Grain yield was higher in durum wheat genotypes Garagylchyg 2, Barakatli 95, Tartar, bread wheat genotypes Giymatli 2/17, Gyrmyzy gul 1, Azamatli 95, Tale 38, Pirshahin 1, 4thFEFWSN50 under irrigated condition. The average grain yields of durum and bread wheat genotypes were 589g/m², 670g/m² under irrigation, 357g/m² and 452g/m² under drought conditions, respectively.

Fig.1. Effect of drought stress on relative water content

Fig. 2. Effect of drought stress on leaf area index of wheat genotypes

Fig. 3. Effect of drought stress on grain yield of wheat genotypes

The reduction of grain yield due to water scarcity was 39% for durum and 33% for bread wheat genotypes. A more significant reduction of

grain yield was revealed in the wheat genotypes Barakatli 95, Alinja 84, Tartar, Tale 38, Akinchi 84, and Ruzi 84. Less reduction of grain yield was

revealed in the genotypes Sharg, Gyrgyz bugda, Nurlu 99, 4thFEFWSN50, and Saratovskaya 29.

CONCLUSION

Drought is the main constraint for many morpho-physiological, biochemical, and agronomical traits of the wheat plant. Physiological traits (gas exchange parameters, photosynthesizing pigments content, leaf water regime parameters, leaf assimilation area per unit area) are very important for the formation of grain yield. Usually, wheat genotypes with high indicators of these traits are sensitive to water scarcity. Physiological breeding allows the screening of wheat genotypes for drought tolerance as well as choosing parents for further hybridization. Wheat genotypes Sharg, Gyrgyz bugda, Nurlu 99, 4thFEFWSN50, and Saratovskaya 29 were tolerant to drought stress.

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Fizioloji göstəricilərinə görə buğda genotiplərinin quraqlığadavamlılığının qiymətləndirilməsi

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Buğda insanların qidalanmasında mühüm ərzaq, eyni zamanda heyvandarlıqda yem bitkisidir. Buğdanın böyümə və inkişafı zamanı su çatışmazlığı məhsuldarlığın əhəmiyyətli azalmasına səbəb olur. Fizioloji əlamətlər müxtəlif buğda genotiplərinin quraqlığa davamlılığına görə qiymətləndirilməsində mühüm əhəmiyyət kəsb edir. Bərk və yumşaq buğda genotiplərinin suvarma və quraqlıq stressi şəraitində fizioloji əlamətləri (qaz mübadiləsi parametrləri, fotosintetik piqmentlərin miqdarı, nisbi su tutumu, yarpaq sahə indeksi) öyrənilmişdir. Tədqiq olunan əlamətlərin yüksək göstəricilərinə malik olan buğda genotipləri adətən quraqlıq stressinə həssas olmuşdur. Şərq, Qırmızı buğda, Nurlu 99, 4th FEFWSN №50 və Saratovskaya 29 buğda genotipləri quraqlıq stressinə davamlı olmuşdur.

Açar sözlər: *Buğda, quraqlıq stressi, fotosintez, xlorofil, nisbi su tutumu, yarpaq sahə indeksi, dən məhsuldarlığı*